

Innovations applied in the design and construction of the Arroyo Vega flood relief tunnel

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ABSTRACT: This paper aims to present experiences and innovations implemented in the flood relief project “Segundo Emisario del Arroyo Vega”, part of Buenos Aires city hydraulic master plan. Works comprised the execution of an 8.4km-long tunnel for relief of the existing sewer network. Tunnel alignment develops in a highly populated area, with important interferences such as two metro lines, three railway lines and a main potable-water tunnel. All tunnel sections extend mostly within firm, silty soils. Overburden varies between 15 and 25m. The downstream section was executed with a 6.1m-diameter EPB-TBM, launched from a 35m-diameter shaft with water table pressures up to 200kPa. Break-in was performed across a watertight, plastic diaphragm wall cell, which allowed safe shaft wall demolition, avoiding use of startup sealing ring, resulting on a very safe TBM launch. The tunnel upstream section, 2.85m in diameter, was executed using Pipe Jacking technology, with the peculiarity of using two-directional launch shafts along its alignment. In order to allow water entrance from existing system –through flow diversion chambers– into the new relief tunnel, openings were made in the TBM tunnel, with connection areas of 4 to 7m². Its design was particularly challenging, given that unbolted segmental lining was used.

KEYWORDS: TBM tunnel, Pipe Jacking, Urban tunnel, Sewer tunnel, Break-in, Monitoring, Unbolted, Segmental lining

1. INTRODUCTION

The basin of “Arroyo Vega” (Vega River) extends entirely within the city of Buenos Aires. The city has an area of 203 km², of which approximately 17 km² belong to this basin (see Figure 1), including the neighbourhoods of Villa Devoto, Agronomía, Parque Chas, Villa Ortúzar, Villa Urquiza, Coghlan, Belgrano y Colegiales.

Figure 1: Buenos Aires city Basins ([1])

The Project “Segundo Emisario del Arroyo Vega” (Arroyo Vega Second Outfall) is part of the hydraulic master plan of Buenos Aires city (reference [1]). This master plan was developed due to the frequent and severe floods that affected the city in at least 12 occasions between 1985 and 2001, all of them with heavy losses, including human lives (see Figure 2).

Construction contract included the execution of a tunnel along 8.4km for relief of the existing sewer network, and its complementary works. These works were carried out by Cartellone-Roggio-Supercemento joint venture.

Geoconsult Buenos Aires developed detailed design and tracked on monitoring during construction.

Tunnel alignment develops in an area of high population density and with important interferences, such as 2 underground metro lines (B and D), 3 railway lines and a potable water distribution tunnel. To

avoid these interferences for almost 6km along the alignment, a relatively deep tunnel was projected, of between 15 and 25m cover. JV Contractor executed this tunnel with a 6.1m diameter EPB-TBM, launched from a 35m-diameter shaft located on “Rio de la Plata” (River Plate) coast, in front of Buenos Aires domestic airport. This launch shaft was adapted in the final stage to operate as an outlet shaft and to allow tunnel emptying for maintenance.

Figure 2: Photograph taken during 2001 flood

Complementary works included the construction of 5 flow diversion chambers and their corresponding connections to the main tunnel. These chambers allow water discharge from existing system into the new relief tunnel, through built-in spillways. Within the connection tunnels, the most important is “Ramal Elcano” (Elcano branch), with 3.0m internal diameter and 450m long, excavated through conventional method.

2. SITE GEOTECHNICAL CONDITIONS

As described by Núñez (1986) (reference [2]), per the geotechnical characteristics of the foundation subsoil, we can divide Buenos Aires City into two main zones:

The first one, which covers the principal urban area of the city, “presents in the upper levels, deposits belonging to Pleistocene.

These deposits include silty and clayey soils, preconsolidated by desiccation, with layers or lenses of cemented soils by calcareous impregnation. The total thickness of these sedimentary deposits is about 25 to 45 m; this part of the profile is the locally so-called ‘Pampeano’ formation.”

The second one, located along the “Río de la Plata” shore and “Riachuelo” valley, presents “soft deposits of clays and plastic silty clayey soils, and/or loose to medium sandy soils, (...) that are included in the locally named ‘Post-Pampeano’ formation belonging to the Holocene.”

“Underlying these formations, we found the ‘Puelches’ fine and dense sands that correspond to the Pliocene Period. Into these dense sands, there is a layer or stratum of plastic clayey silt or silty clay, a very plastic soil, approximately 10 m or a little thicker. This greenish-grey or blueish clay is very stiff and generally normally consolidated under the loads imposed by the biggest thickness of the ‘Pampeano’ profile.”

Geotechnical parameters of the strata described above are shown in Table 1 for reference.

Table 1: Geotechnical Parameters

Symbol	Parameter	Layer					
		PP	PS	PM	PI	Pu	Pa
γ [kN/m ³]	Unit weight	17	19	19	19	21	17
c' [kPa]	Effective cohesion	0	10	30	20	0	0
Φ' [°]	Effective internal friction angle	27	29	32	31	35	25
E_{ur}^{ref} [MPa]	Unloading/reloading stiffness	115	100	270	195	260	85
E_{oed}^{ref} [MPa]	Tangent stiffness in oedometer test	40	35	90	65	90	30
E_{50}^{ref} [MPa]	Secant stiffness in drained triaxial test	40	35	90	65	90	30
OCR [-]	Over-consolidation ratio	1	2	3	3	-	1.2
K_0 [-]	Horizontal pressure coefficient	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.4	0.5
k [m/day]	Permeability	0.05	0.9	0.9	0.01	10	-

Where:

PP: “Post-Pampeano” PS: Upper “Pampeano”
 PM: Medium “Pampeano” PI: Lower “Pampeano”
 Pu: “Puelches” Pa: “Paranaense” or Blue clays

3. TBM LAUNCH SHAFT

3.1. General description

Works began with the execution of the launch shaft, 35m internal diameter, which would later act as an outlet shaft, discharging its water into the “Río de la Plata” through an outlet channel. Its diaphragm walls were executed with hydro-mill trench cutter and are 1.20m thick and almost 60m deep, with a 1.00m thick bottom slab that leaves an interior depth of approximately 26.50 m.

Diaphragm walls penetrate in the so-called blue clays and isolate the Puelche sands to guarantee water tightness inside the shaft and hence safety against heave, given Puelche sands are a powerful aquifer. In the tender design, the bottom level of diaphragm walls was set on -51.00masl, but due to the variability of blue clays ceiling level observed on new boreholes, a bottom level of -56.00masl was finally adopted (see Figure 3). Before the beginning of the excavation process we dewatered the shaft, which allowed a fully dry soil excavation. Shaft excavation concluded in January 2018,

then bottom slab execution took place and finally, in March 2018, TBM thrust frame was mounted (see Figure 4).

Figure 3: Launch shaft stratigraphic profile

Figure 4: TBM inside launch shaft

3.2. Diaphragm wall panel arrangement

Given the depth of the diaphragm walls –necessary to reach the so-called blue clays–, verticality of the panels was a concern. Frequently, in circular shafts executed with hydromills, secondary panels have outward deviations due to the wedge effect generated by the primary panels during mill process, compromising the water tightness of the structure as well as decreasing the contact surface between panels, increasing compression stress between walls.

A new panel layout was adopted in order to mitigate wall deviation, executing the secondary walls by parallel milling the primary walls (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Adopted wall panel arrangement (primary walls in green – secondary walls in pink)

Although contact surfaces between panels were maximized – through parallel joints between primary and secondary walls–, since faceted geometry must be achieved within primary panels (executed in three bites) this will increase compression stress anyway. Using this geometry, practically no deviations were detected, significantly improving water tightness of the shaft along its entire height and, hence, increasing its global safety.

3.3. Break-in design

The design involved a watertight diaphragm wall cell adjacent to the circular shaft, to prevent water entry during break-in process. This proposal replaced the tender design solution, which involved a starter block to be made with jet grouting technique. We based this decision on recent deficient jet grouting applications in formations such as “Pampeano” and “Puelche”. The cell was executed with plastic concrete and had an inner length of around 17m to house the TBM shield plus 3 segmental lining rings (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Launch shaft plan view (sketch)

Once the interior of the plastic concrete cell was dewatered, this design allowed manual demolition works in the launch shaft diaphragm wall, without water presence (Figure 7). Demolition took place in three stages and during each stage an arc-shaped excavation was executed, protected with a shotcrete coating. This enabled TBM launch without starting seal and no water pressure, directly into the soil mass without need to wear cutting tools for diaphragm wall demolition.

Figure 7: Photograph taken during execution of the opening

Face stability checking was necessary during execution of the opening. We modelled this sequence numerically to verify that face

stability safety factor was adequate. A three-dimensional finite element model was performed, using ‘Hardening Soil with small strain stiffness’ constitutive model (HS-Small) for all geotechnical units. Figure 8 shows PLAXIS 3D mesh (reference [3]) with the resulting failure wedge (overlapped).

Figure 8: 3D numerical finite element model for break-in evaluation

3.4. Monitoring during construction

Launch shaft monitoring project included installation of surface settlement pins, inclinometers and piezometers. Figure 9 shows groundwater levels inside and outside the shaft and inside the plastic cell, as well as the evolution of those levels in relation with different project milestones. Groundwater level inside launch shaft was maintained between -30 and -32masl, pumping out very small flow rates (approx. 1.2 L/sec), which demonstrate that blue clays bottom plug is effective and that diaphragm walls embedment length within this soil layer is sufficient. Likewise, groundwater level inside the plastic cell was also maintained in approx. -32.00masl until the plastic wall was broken by the TBM.

Figure 9: Groundwater levels registered in piezometers

4. TBM TUNNEL UNDER LA PAMPA STREET

4.1. General description

First section of the main flood relief tunnel was executed with a TBM (EPB) of 6.1m diameter, named “Elisa”. Tunnel boring began on April 2018 and concluded by the end of June 2019. Total excavation length was 5,900m.

Before construction works started, we decided to modify tunnel elevation proposed in tender design, trying to avoid, as much as possible, excavation of “Puelche” sands, since conditioning of this sands using EPB technology is considerably more complicated than “Pampeano” soils. With this modification, we also avoided mixed face geotechnical conditions in almost the entire project. Therefore, tunnel elevation was adjusted so that TBM face was located mostly

between lower stratum of “Pampeano” formation and transition with “Puelche” sands, as shown in Figure 10.

With this new elevation, overburden varied between 20 and 30m and groundwater level varied from 14 to 29m, with respect to tunnel axis. Main interferences, which set boundary conditions for elevation design, were a potable-water tunnel from state company AYSA and the D and B metro lines.

Figure 10: TBM tunnel elevation

We also adjusted tender design alignment to avoid the curve and counter-curve of 200m radius at the excavation beginning, which actually was a limit curve radius for TBM drive (see Figure 11). This change was of great importance, because allowed to perform machine start-up and staff training in a practically straight section (1000m radius curve). With the new alignment, the minimum curve radius in the whole project was 600m. Still, designed segmental ring could describe curves above 235m radius.

Figure 11: TBM tunnel alignment modification at the beginning

4.2. Segmental lining ring design

Segmental lining ring was re-designed after bidding phase, in order to solve several design issues detected in tender project. Tender design involved a 5+1, right-left ring arrangement, which only allowed two possible relative positions and hence restricted significantly tunnel direction changes and alignment possibilities.

We adopted a 6+0, universal ring arrangement, which owned the advantage of having a single ring to describe any path, with six possible relative positions. This arrangement also brought advantages from segment production point of view, since all segments had approximately the same volume –although each one had different geometry– and therefore processes were optimized. Ring was composed by a trapezoidal segment called ‘counter-key’ –erected in the first place–, four parallelogram-shaped segments and another trapezoidal segment called ‘key’, which was the last to be erected. Segmental ring arrangement can be seen in Figure 12.

One disadvantage of this arrangement was given by key segment erection difficulties. In order to switch from original 5+1 arrangement to a 6+0 configuration, it was necessary to extend the machine tail shield and thrust cylinders stroke, given that a 5+1 ring

can be mounted with greater overlap between segments than a 6+0 ring.

Figure 12: Segmental ring 6+0 arrangement (intrados, unrolled view)

As we adopted a universal ring-type, key segment could be at any position, which means the ring could be assembled from top to bottom. For this reason, a structural check was required in order to verify if counter-key segment could resist its own weight, supported only by connectors in cantilever conditions (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Counter-key segment in cantilever conditions (sketch)

In addition, we proposed using special connectors in circumferential joints and guiding rods in radial joints, instead of typical mounting bolts (see joint details in Figure 14 and Figure 15). With this unbolted segmental lining, we sought to reduce the roughness introduced by bolt recesses (see Figure 16). This was a major innovation for TBM sewage tunnels in Argentina.

Water tightness in segmental lining joints was provided by EPDM sealing gaskets. We employed an anchored gasket, installed directly in a recess inside the segment mould before concrete cast, which actually saved a step in the production cycle. Their main disadvantage lied in the fact that its anchors introduce a weakness surface that can split the segment corner when the gasket is compressed (see Figure 17).

Figure 14: Segmental lining radial joints

Figure 15: Segmental lining circumferential joints

Figure 16: Unbolted segmental lining in TBM tunnel

Figure 18: Connection construction stages (simplified sketch)

Figure 17: Corner failure surface evaluated

4.3. Design of openings

For the three connections of the existing network with TBM tunnel, tender design posed the execution of a diaphragm wall shaft with a jet grouting bottom plug before TBM drive-through. This shaft

would be penetrated and crossed by the TBM and, then, the connection works would be done inside. This design would have involved a dirty jobsite in a highly-populated area.

Our approach differed from tender project, as we proposed reaching the TBM tunnel through the connection galleries with the existing network, in order to avoid the removal and relocation of important interferences, and to avoid surface occupation. These connection galleries were executed once the TBM had already passed through the connection site (see Figure 18).

We developed a 3D structural model with SAP2000 (reference [4]) to evaluate the behaviour of the TBM tunnel with the opening and to design concrete collar and its connections with the segments. Segments were modelled as bedded shells and connections between adjacent segments were modelled through different types of springs. Mechanical properties of these springs were defined considering whether it was a radial or a circumferential joint.

Temporary internal steel connections between segments were placed before excavation above the TBM tunnel took place, in order to ensure tunnel stability during concrete collar execution (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: Temporary internal connections

Figure 20: 3D structural model for an opening. Horizontal displacements map

During the excavation stages until TBM tunnel crown level was reached, the gallery above TBM tunnel had to bear cantilever support conditions, since vertical connection structure was not yet executed. This circumstance was taken into account in design phase. Excavation and cast of the collar took place in two stages. Figure 21 shows excavation for the first half of the collar. Blue-coloured annular void backfill can be easily observed.

After excavation, drillings were performed on the segments in order to install connection bars with the concrete collar. We specified DYWIDAG bars of 32mm diameter (see Figure 22).

Once the first half of the collar was built, excavation of the other half was performed and, next, the rest of the collar was cast.

Finally, drillings were made in order to allow segment cutting with diamond wire (see Figure 23).

Figure 21: Excavation above TBM Tunnel

Figure 22: Collar reinforcement and connection bars

Figure 23: Segment cutting with diamond wire

4.4. Tracking of TBM operational parameters and monitoring during construction

Figure 24 shows excavation progress as a time function. We can observe that, since Ring No. 275 was placed (31/07/2018), the advance rate is practically constant and equal to about 12.7 rings per calendar day. We recorded the only exception at Ring No. 1957, during work interruption between Christmas and New Year's Day. In this graph, we also point out the dates on which major crossings under the six most relevant interferences took place.

The average TBM utilization factor was about 35%, with a boring advance time of 20 to 25 minutes and a ring assembly time of 25 to 30 minutes.

Figure 24: Excavation progress (# Ring) vs. Time chart

Crossing under metro B Line was the closest in the whole drive, with a 2.50m gap between TBM tunnel crown and B Line tunnel invert. We prepared a 3D geotechnical model to evaluate the effects of relief tunnel excavation on metro tunnel. This model simulated the sequence of each machine advance and ring installation stage. We compared 3D model results with monitoring data of the TBM tunnel. In general, instruments revealed very small displacements, similar to those predicted by the 3D numerical model.

5. PIPE JACKING TUNNEL UNDER NUEVA YORK AND BALLIVIAN STREET

5.1. General description

Upstream section of the main flood relief tunnel had a diameter of 2.4m and 2400m length, extending through the Middle "Pampeano" (firm, highly cemented silts and clays).

This section had a smaller overburden, between 10 and 12m with respect to tunnel axis. However, it can be classified as a deep tunnel,

given its overburden-diameter ratio. Groundwater level to tunnel axis varied between 4 and 9m. Main interference was the existing “Arroyo Vega” sewer pipe¹, which ran parallel on a higher elevation.

Figure 25: Pipe jacking tunnel elevation

For this section, the Contractor decided to use Pipe Jacking technology instead of the conventional methodology proposed on tender design. Driving a conventional, manual excavation as planned in tender design would force to dig provisional pits every 120-150m, as well as drainage galleries along tunnel alignment for dewatering purposes. Moreover, these construction pits would have to be located within a narrow street, plenty of existing subsurface services such as gas pipes, sewers, etc. On the other hand, Pipe Jacking methodology allowed excavation under groundwater level, with no personnel in the excavation front, requiring almost half of the construction pits originally estimated. With this decision, Contractor sought to reduce surface affectation and increase works safety.

For this purpose, we designed 3 launch pits and 4 reception pits to complete 6 drive stages with AVN machine, optimizing tunnel boring distances.

Precast concrete pipes had 2.8m external diameter, with 3m length and 20cm thickness. Pipes were designed with a ‘bell and spigot’ joint type, where water tightness was provided by a wedge-shaped slip-ring elastomeric seal (see Figure 26 for joint detail).

Excavation began in August 2018 and concluded on August 2019.

Figure 26: Typical precast pipe joint detail

Figure 27: Typical precast pipe

5.2. Design of bidirectional launch pits

Pipe jacking launch pits had a special design. Firstly, because of the limited space available given to the presence of interferences and secondly, since we needed to launch the AVN machine in both directions from each launch shaft.

To keep surface occupation as reduced as possible, we sized the pit to allow AVN machine descent and, at future tunnel level, we created the room for machine assembly through 3m-long adits upstream and downstream (see Figure 28 and Figure 29).

Besides, we devised a thrust wall with a circular hole to enable machine launch in the opposite direction. Because of this opening, a steel frame had to be designed in order to transfer eccentric jack loads to the thrust wall concrete mass (see Figure 30 and Figure 31).

Figure 28: Launch shaft elevation

¹Actually, “Arroyo Vega” is a natural river which was cased (tunneled) during first half of 20th century as a consequence of city growth.

Figure 29: Launch shaft plan view

Figure 30: Designed thrust wall

Figure 31: Thrust frame positioning

We performed a 3D numerical simulation of launch pit execution in order to verify bearing capacity of soil mass behind thrust wall and evaluate impact on the existing sewer pipe during construction. A finite element model was developed in PLAXIS 3D (reference [3])

using HS-Small constitutive model for all soils (see Figure 32). Resulting failure wedge can be seen in Figure 33.

Thrust wall reinforcement design was done through a structural model in SAP2000 (see Figure 34), adopting a strut and tie mechanism. We based this choice on the considerable thickness of the structure and the presence of concentrated jacks loads. Given this situation, we consider that Bernoulli-Navier hypothesis was not valid.

Figure 32: 3D numerical finite element model for launch pit

Figure 33: Resulting failure wedge behind thrust wall

Figure 34: Thrust wall strut and tie model

Figure 35: Launch pit ready for AVN machine assembly

5.3. Tracking of AVN machine operational parameters

During AVN machine operation we recorded jacking load, cutting wheel speed, cutting wheel torque and advance rate parameters. Table 2 shows mean values for some of these parameters for each drive.

Table 2: AVN machine mean operational parameters

Drive		Parameter			
From	To	Length (m)	Duration (days)	Advance rate (pipes/day)	Cutting wheel speed (rpm)
PL1	PR1	438	61	2.4	4.2
PL1	PR2	435	35	4.1	4.5
PL2	PR2	468	42	3.7	4.3
PL2	PR3	420	42	3.3	4.4
PL3	PR4	471	41	3.8	4.5
PL3	PR3	114	8	4.8	4.5

As an example, Figure 36 shows excavation evolution as a time function during tunnel drive from PL1 to PR1.

Figure 36: Advance (pipe number) vs. Time

We estimated jacking loads according to Hough & Milligan (reference [5]). As specified by the authors, “forces due to face load will be relatively low in cohesive ground and related to the excavation and trimming of the shield”.

Likewise, “friction forces in a stable bore are a function of the weight of the pipes (W) to the local interface friction coefficient (δ)”. A factor of 25% was added to cover minor misalignments (see Eq. (1)).

$$F = 1.25 W \tan(\delta) = 1.25 \cdot (40.8 \text{ kN/m}) \cdot \tan(0.8 \cdot 30^\circ) = 22.4 \text{ kN/m} \quad (1)$$

Figure 37 shows estimated and actual jacking load vs. distance along tunnel drive from PL1 to PR1. Influence of interjacking operation starting halfway can be slightly noted.

Figure 37: Jacking load vs. Distance

Figure 38: Jacking of the first pipe inside launch pit

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have presented the most relevant geotechnical and structural challenges associated with the execution of the Arroyo Vega flood relief tunnel.

We have described the design of the TBM launch shaft, whose adopted wall panel geometry resulted in optimum water tightness. In particular, the solution adopted for break-in, employing a plastic concrete diaphragm wall cell, resulted simple and successful on Buenos Aires city geotechnical conditions. We achieved a safe and water-free TBM launch without cutting tools wear.

Regarding TBM tunnel design, we have detailed the adopted solution for the execution of the openings, which allow water entrance from the existing network. This solution was quite complex given that a non-bolted ring was adopted, although was effective and avoided all the problems associated with an open pit excavation, specially carrying out a massive, muddy jobsite in a densely-populated area.

The pipe jacking section, originally planned with conventional excavation, allowed a smaller impact on the surface and the execution of a safer work. This document shows the adopted solution of bidirectional launch pits, which were the biggest challenge in this sector. These double pits required precise pipe positioning at the end of each drive stage, flush with the thrust wall, in order to allow jack frame standing for launch maneuver in the opposite direction. However, this design achieved the best solution for minimizing surface impact, avoiding jobsite relocation for each drive stage in a highly-populated area.

Finally, we have also shown the most relevant results of the monitoring system implemented in each sector.

7. REFERENCES

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